

Factors explaining the outcomes of enforced return and post-return

Working Paper

Project Title	FAiR: Finding Agreement in Return
Project Acronym	FAiR
Grant Agreement No	101094828
Start Date of Project	01.05.2023
Duration of Project	42 months
Project Coordinator	Arjen Leerkes
Title of Deliverable	Working paper on the factors explaining the outcomes of enforced return and post-return
Deliverable Number	D2.2
Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Type of Document	R – Document report
Work Package	WP2
Version	1.0
Expected Delivery Date	31.07.2024
Authors	Ana Maria Torres Chedraui, Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) Arjen Leerkes, Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) Michael Sinnige, Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) Laura Cleton, Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR)
Filename	D2.2 Outcomes of enforced return.doc

FUNDING

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement 101094828

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Change	Pages
0.1	07-06-2024	Draft submitted to the internal reviewer (Jiancheng Gu, University for Continuing Education Krems, UWK)	30
1.0	19-07-2024	Revised based on internal review	35

Table of contents

Executive summary	4
Acknowledgement	5
Introduction.....	5
Section 1: Enforced Return outcomes	6
Conceptualisation of enforced return.....	6
Non-policy drivers of enforced return.....	7
Policy drivers of enforced return.....	12
Section 2: Post-return Outcomes	17
Conceptualisation of post-return outcomes.....	17
Non-policy drivers of post-return outcomes.....	18
Policy drivers of post-return outcomes.....	23
Preliminary conclusions and further research.....	25
References.....	27

Executive summary

This working paper examines the determinants of enforced return and post-return outcomes for migrants, focusing on the role of policies and various non-policy factors at micro, meso, and macro levels. In line with Deliverable 2.2.1, this working paper departs from the idea that enforced return encompasses not only physically forced deportations but also voluntary returns induced by state policies and conditions. Policies in host countries that limit access to employment, social services, or legal protections often push migrants towards return as a perceived better option.

The study reveals several key insights:

- Voluntary returns generally provide better prospects for reintegration due to the preparation and stronger social support networks. Conversely, forced returns are often associated with stigma, lack of preparedness, and psychological issues, especially among children.
- Various policy and non-policy factors determine the enforced return and post-return outcomes, at the micro, meso and macro level.
- Non-Policy Determinants:
 - **Micro Level:** Individual factors like legal status, ability to save money, age, gender, and family situation influence the decision to return and reintegration success.
 - **Meso Level:** Social networks in both host and home countries, stigma associated with return, and community reception play crucial roles.
 - **Macro Level:** Socio-economic and safety conditions in both host and home countries, including employment opportunities, political stability, and safety, are critical.
- Policy Determinants:
 - **Micro Level:** Focuses on the perceptions of migrants and returnees regarding host country policies, including their enforcement, effectiveness, and legitimacy.
 - **Meso Level:** Examines the role of sanctuary cities and NGOs in moderating the effects and enforcement levels of host country policies.
 - **Macro Level:** Involves host country policies and programs designed to enforce and encourage return, including return and readmission agreements with receiving states to facilitate this process. It also encompasses policies in countries of origin aimed at stimulating return

The paper highlights the challenges faced by returnees, such as stigmatization, economic reintegration difficulties, and family disruptions. It recommends coordinated actions between host and origin countries to improve post-return outcomes for returnees. Further research is needed to quantitatively assess the impact of stringent host country policies, explore the effects of different return agreements, and focus on South-South return processes. Monitoring the human rights situation of returnees is crucial for sustainable reintegration.

In summary, the paper emphasizes that successful reintegration and sustainable return require a holistic approach, considering both policy and non-policy determinants across different levels.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Kina Sato (EUR) for providing research assistance and Gu Jiancheng (UWK) for providing useful comments on an earlier draft of the manuscript and for bringing additional publications to our attention.

Introduction

Migrant return often symbolises the realisation of accumulated wealth, the achievement of personal goals, and the desire to reunite with loved ones in their home country. However, this is not always the case and not in particular when the state has induced the person to return, through direct or indirect means (Battistella 2018). The state uses direct means when it employs coercive measures to compel individuals to leave the country or sponsors return programs (Newland and Salant 2018, ECRE 2018, Leerkes et al. 2017, Webber 2011). And it uses indirect means when it creates unfavourable conditions for migrants, such as limiting access to employment, social services, or legal protections, effectively pushing them to choose return as a perceived better option (Pluymen 2002, van Houte 2014, Leerkes 2016, Kos et al. 2016). Since both forms of return require the presence of the state, it can be said that the state enforces those returns.

As part of the state power to control migration and enforce returns, governments issue return decisions or expulsion orders when individuals do not meet the requirements for legal stay. This can happen due to visa expiration, illegal entry, or rejection of asylum applications, among other reasons. According to the EU Return Directive, EU Member States and certain associated countries, such as Switzerland and Norway, are obliged to grant a grace period for voluntary departure, allowing migrants subject to a return decision to comply voluntarily with the expulsion order. The duration of this grace period varies per country but should not be shorter than 7 days. During this grace period (and sometimes even before it starts), states typically activate their return processes to encourage voluntary compliance, which may include counselling for migrants and, in some cases, financial assistance for their return journey (Lietaert 2022, Leerkes et al. 2017, Cleton and Chauvin 2020). This process is known as ‘assisted voluntary return’, and because it involves state intervention, while continued stay in the territory is not allowed, it can be considered a form of *enforced return*.

Several factors influence whether individuals who receive a decision to return, or are in a situation where the state could issue such a decision, choose to use the grace period to leave the country, possibly by enrolling in assisted return programs or attempt to evade authorities and stay irregularly in the country, which entails a risk on deportation.¹ These factors include both policy and non-policy elements, such as the personal circumstances of migrants, including their social connections and networks in both the receiving and home countries, as well as the broader structural conditions and governmental policies in both countries. This paper will delve into these factors in greater detail.

Just because someone returns to their home country does not guarantee they will stay there. Research indicates that returnees often try to emigrate again (Schuster and Majidi 2013). This tendency typically

¹ Apprehended irregular migrants usually do not get the grace period and are detained.

arises when the returnee struggles to reintegrate successfully into their home country. Policy makers often refer to the concept of sustainable return to point out the successful socio-economic reintegration of returnees into their home country (OECD 2024). Sustainable return hinges on a combination of individual motivations, societal connections, and governmental policies, all of which will be dealt with in more detail in this paper.

In subsequent sections, we will examine both policy and non-policy determinants of enforced return as well as post-return outcomes. Policy determinants encompass factors directly influenced by government policies, laws, and regulations governing migration, returns, and reintegration. Non-policy determinants include broader societal, economic, and contextual factors that indirectly affect the likelihood of returns and successful reintegration. We will analyse these determinants at micro (individual factors), meso (intermediary institutions and networks), and macro (societal and structural) levels.

It is important to note, however, that distinguishing between policy and non-policy factors as well as between micro-, meso- and macro-levels can be challenging, as they often interact with each other (van Wijck 2008). For instance, access to public services and welfare rights, although influenced by macro-level policies, can impact a migrant's decision to remain in a country, depending on their personal needs (such as health and age) and family situation (such as children), which are micro- and meso-level non-policy factors. Similarly, the decision to enforce return is not solely driven by macro-level policy considerations (such as the aim to reduce irregular migration or to uphold the law) but is also influenced by non-policy factors, such as the migrant's personal circumstances. In cases where these personal circumstances are particularly compelling, such as health concerns or the presence of minors, the state often provides avenues for humanitarian stay or street-level bureaucrats may opt not to enforce strict legal measures (Cleton 2022).

For clarity, we will present the determinants of return and post-return outcomes separately. However, we acknowledge that these factors can overlap. For example, individuals who anticipate unfavourable post-return conditions—such as stigma or lack of job opportunities—may be less willing to cooperate with their return compared to those who expect favourable conditions upon returning.

This study incorporates both qualitative and quantitative studies. The choice of incorporating both types of studies in this literature review follows from the wide scope of the topic that can be approached from different angles. Recent methodological work has stressed the need for having both type of studies to achieve a full picture of social phenomenon (Panke 2018).

Section 1: Enforced Return outcomes

Conceptualisation of enforced return

The concept of enforced return underscores the significant role of the state both in facilitating the act of return and influencing the decision-making process. This influence manifests in various ways: directly and indirectly. It is *directly* when the state employs coercion using its hard power or when the state sponsors programs and uses its soft powers to compel individuals to return; and it is *indirectly*, when migrants opt to return due to unfavourable circumstances induced by the state, such as restricted access to opportunities or social services, prompting them to view return as a preferable choice amid challenging conditions.

Enforced return, as understood through the deportability concept of De Genova (2002), encompasses a wide spectrum of scenarios, extending beyond instances of physical force to include all returns

following a return decision or when the state holds the authority to issue such a decision (to all irregular migrants). This comprehensive definition encompasses forced returns as well as so-called “voluntary” returns (whether they are “assisted” or not), which may involve different levels of coercion or inducement. Crucially, enforced return also encompasses cases where the state influences migrants’ decisions to return due to contextual conditions in the host country. The concept of enforced return, whether direct or indirect, highlights the pervasive presence of the state in shaping return migration dynamics.

While the discussion that follows will primarily focus on return to the country of citizenship, the framework of enforced return provides a holistic view for examining return dynamics and the state’s role regardless of whether the migrant returns to the country of citizenship or to a third country.

Non-policy drivers of enforced return

The literature review that follows aims to explore the factors influencing individuals’ decisions regarding returning voluntarily, awaiting enforced return (through forced return or assisted return mechanisms), or remaining irregular in the host country. Previous research has categorised these non-policy factors into structural and individual levels (Black et al. 2004, Koser and Kuschminder 2015). At the structural level, we examine macro-level conditions in both the home and host countries, while the individual level encompasses personal attributes (micro-level) and the social connections and networks of the returnee (meso-level). Expanding on this framework, we will also explore how individuals’ beliefs and perceptions influence their interpretation of these contexts, attributes, and networks.

Enforced return outcomes are therefore dependent on host states, states of origin, and migrants’ desires, opportunities, and cognitive beliefs that may or not be true. To guide our examination, we will adopt the DBO model (desires—e.g. desire to reunite with family—, cognitive beliefs —e.g. perceived duty to be with family or the belief that the asylum decision was unfair—, and opportunities—e.g. improved conditions in country of return—) developed by Hedstrom (2005). It is crucial to recognize that the decision to return or not is shaped not only by external factors—such as the individual’s perception of the external world and incentives—but also by internal processes, such as the desire to conform to community norms and personal beliefs, with the aim of minimising cognitive dissonance.

Some sources that have been incorporated in the literature review discuss return migration in a broad sense, without delving into specific forms of return or the legal status of migrants. This broader focus offers valuable insights into understanding why individuals choose voluntary returns over waiting for the state to enforce their return, as the person who chooses to return voluntarily still makes a decision that allows them to overcome enforced returns. *Table 1* below summarises the non-policy factors at play.

Table 1 Non-policy determinants of Enforced Return

Non-Policy determinants of Enforced return		
Micro	Meso	Macro
<i>Level of integration in the host country (employment proficiency language of host country, education, children in host country)</i>	<i>Social networks in the country of return (family ties and connections in the country of origin, return of families, remittances)</i>	<i>Socio-economic and safety conditions in the host country</i>

<i>Individual characteristics (age at the moment of migration, gender)</i>	<i>Stigmatisation for participating in AVR programmes</i>	<i>Socio-political, economic and safety conditions in the country of return (safety, economic prosperity, civil rights, political freedom, cessation of conflict, peace agreements, corruption)</i>
--	---	---

Socio-economic and safety conditions in the host country. Just as economic development and prosperity can serve as magnets for migration, periods of crisis often compel individuals to consider returning to their home countries. However, the decision to return is multifaceted and influenced by a variety of factors which combined with the crisis itself prompts individuals to return. For instance, crises can exacerbate feelings of discrimination among migrants, further influencing their decision-making process (Abaunza 2024). Family obligations back home, particularly during times of crisis can weigh heavily on migrants’ minds (Abaunza 2024, Bastia 2011). Additionally, the financial preparedness of individuals for their return journey can also significantly impact their decision-making process, returning empty-handed is not an option for many migrants (Bastia 2011).

The decision to return during times of crisis is a complex interplay of socio-economic, safety, personal and policy factors, with individuals navigating various challenges and considerations before making their final choice.

Level of integration in the host country. The level of integration does not always have a clear impact on return migration. Structural integration, particularly factors like employment and income, are sometimes found to have no effect on returns. Additionally, sociocultural integration, such as language proficiency, is often found to have a negative effect.

With regards to employment in the host country, Dustmann (1996) found that it could negatively influence the decision to return. Drawing from data from Germany, Dustmann (1996) observed that having employment in the host country tends to diminish intentions to return. Conversely, individuals who are unemployed, particularly those lacking stable full-time employment, demonstrate an increased inclination to return (Constant and Massey 2002). Interestingly, while earnings themselves do not seem to significantly affect return intentions, unemployment does (Constant and Massey 2002). In a study with broader geographical coverage, Zakirova and Buzurukov (2021) found that unemployment in the host country was associated with reduced returns. This phenomenon could be explained by the fact that individuals contemplating return sometimes feel compelled to amass sufficient capital before doing so. Consequently, unemployment may, in certain instances, prolong individuals’ stays in the host country.

The level of education of the migrant has a mixed impact on return decisions. Individuals with more years of schooling are less likely to return, due to better job opportunities and higher wages in the host society (Dustmann 1996). However, for those who have already plans to return, years of schooling have had a positive influence on the likelihood of returning (Dustmaan 1996). This can be explained as access to better jobs enables them to save more, facilitating a quicker return to their home country (de Haas and Fokkema 2011, Constant and Massey 2002).

Proficiency in the language of the host country reduces the likelihood of return due to improved integration and access to better job opportunities (Dustmann 1996). This finding is consistent with de Haas and Fokkema’s (2011) research, which suggests that higher levels of sociocultural integration in the host country are associated with decreased intentions to return.

The presence of children in the host country has a negative impact on return migration. Individuals with children are more likely to integrate into the host society, often benefiting from their children's integration and social networks. Conversely, having children in the home country has the opposite effect, increasing the likelihood of return migration (Dustmann 1996, Constant and Massey 2002).

The presence of children can also affect enforced returns. On one hand, the presence of children could support the acceleration of assisted voluntary returns under the argument that it is in the best interest of the child to be returned to their place of origin to end their situation of irregularity and uncertainty. On the other hand, it may also serve as a reason not to enforce return on them due to their well-integration in the country (Cleton 2022).

Socio-political, economic and safety conditions in the country of return. Qualitative studies examining the factors influencing migrants' decisions to participate in assisted voluntary return programs offer conflicting views on the significance of conditions in their home countries for influencing return decisions. While Black et al. (2004) found that peace, security and safety in the home country were important factors influencing the decision to return; Koser and Kuschminder (2015) found these factors to be less relevant compared to the conditions and policies in the host country. Their research, conducted through interviews and focus groups among returnees, revealed that lack of employment rights or negative asylum application decisions were primary reasons for return. This disparity in findings may stem from the timing of the interviews; those surveyed by Koser and Kuschminder (2015) had already returned, whereas participants in the studies by Black et al. (2004) were still residing in their host country. This difference could be attributed to the realisation upon return that conditions in their home country were less dire than anticipated, and to the reassessment of the difficulties they endeavour while in the host country (Koser and Kuschminder 2015).

Klinthall's (2007) study offers an insightful perspective regarding the conditions in the country of return. Using binomial regression analysis, Klinthall observed a significant difference in return migration from Sweden to Chile after democratisation compared to return migration to Poland following the end of the communist regime. This difference appears to be driven by the economic growth experienced by Chile immediately after democratisation, which was lacking in Poland. Similarly, van Wijk (2008) found through interviews to native counselling in the Netherlands, that both the economic situation and the safety in the country of return were important factors for their clients to choose returning. Improved safety and economic conditions in the country of return attract migrants to return, while deteriorating or unfavourable economic and safety conditions had a deter-effect. While Kurds from the Northern part of Iraq were willing to return because of perceived safety, Afghans were not. In addition, owning property in the country of return was considered a pull-factor on return, while lacking property was seen as a deter-factor, especially if real estate prices had significantly increased after conflict (van Wijk 2008). Based on structured interviews with 108 asylum seekers who had received a return decision, or were at risk of receiving such a decision, Leerkes, Galloway and Kromhout (2011) found that perceived safety in the country of origin was the strongest determinant of respondents' return intentions, and that low return intentions were primarily explained by perceived unsafety in the country of origin.

From interviews with Somali and Afghan asylum seekers in the UK, Zimmermann (2011) found that they all desired to return to their home countries under conditions of safety and socio-economic security similar to what they had before the armed conflict erupted. Quantitative studies have reached similar conclusions. Through the use of regression analysis using micro-data, Leerkes et al. (2017) found that participation in assisted voluntary return programs in The Netherlands was more likely to rise when the country of return offered political stability, ensured civil rights, and boasted prosperous living standards. Similarly, Zakirova and Buzurukov (2021) found that both improved political and economic conditions in the home country attracted voluntary returns. However, their regression

analysis highlighted the predominant impact of political factors. Notably, factors such as increased liberty and freedom, cessation of conflict, and peace agreements were among the key political drivers influencing return decisions and access to education in the home country, the key economic predictor of return migration. A Master thesis using micro-data for Sweden similarly found that improvements in the security situation in the country of origin were associated with more assisted returns, but counterintuitively found improved economic conditions decreased returns (Hemberg 2022).

Aligned with the political and economic landscape of the return country, several studies highlight the critical role of corruption in influencing migrant return decisions (Tsuda 2009, Oeppen 2005). The prevalence of corruption in countries of origin serves as a deterrent for migrants contemplating return. Corruption not only complicates the attainment of job positions based on merit but also demands additional effort and skills to navigate daily interactions with public officials (Paasche 2022). Moreover, corruption presents challenges in the development of assisted return programs. On one hand, such programs must ensure the returnee's protection from corrupt practices, as they may become targets due to the economic assistance they receive (OECD 2020). On the other hand, these programs must establish mechanisms to prevent the returnee from engaging in corrupt practices (e.g. deviating the purpose for which the assistance was given) (Paasche, 2018).

Social networks in the country of return. The presence of family ties and connections in the country of origin can influence both regular and irregular migrants' decisions to return.

Having a partner from the country of origin appears to have a positive impact on return migration. The analysis of Dustmann (1996) based on micro-level data for Germany suggests that married couples, particularly those where neither spouse is a native, are more likely to return (Dustmann, 1996). Furthermore, the likelihood of return increases if the couple resides in their home country (Dustmann, 1996, Constant and Massey 2002), indicating that ties to the home country strongly influence return migration. Furthermore, the qualitative research of Koser and Kuschminder (2015) shows that irregular migrants were not disconnected from their families in countries of origin. In their qualitative study, they found for instance that, the illness of a family member or the desire to reunite with loved ones was frequently cited by asylum seekers with a rejected decision as a significant factor influencing their decision to return (Koser and Kuschminder 2015).

Research conducted by Yendaw (2013) reveals that the primary motivation for Ghanaians to return to their homeland was driven by family considerations (27%), coupled with a desire to invest in their country (19%). A significant portion of the respondents (85%) disclosed that they received information about the country prior to their decision to return, with parents (42%) or friends (24%) serving as the main sources of such information. This underscores the close ties between returnees and their familial and social networks in their country of origin and their role in providing essential information and influencing the decision-making on return.

The act of sending remittances serves as an indicator of the networks and connections individuals maintain in their country of origin. However, the impact of remittance sending on return intentions is complex and less straightforward than the presence of family members alone. In some instances, sending remittances increased the likelihood of return (Constant and Massey 2002), while in others, remittances sent to the community reduced return intentions (de Haas and Fokkema 2011). These mixed effects indicate that remittances serve multiple purposes beyond economic investment. They not only help sustain family members back home but also cultivate social and emotional ties. While remittances may increase return intentions due to the desire to reunite with family, they can also decrease such intentions by fostering a sense of ongoing obligation and connection to the home community.

The multivariate analysis conducted by Brekke (2015) in Norway revealed that couples and families larger than two were more likely to enrol in voluntary return programs than single individuals. On the contrary, Leerkes et al. (2017) found that in the Netherlands couples and families with children were less likely to use assisted return programs than single men. This shows that evidence on this issue is still unsettled and may require further exploration.

Individual characteristics. Individual characteristics influence return. Of relevance are age at the moment of migration and gender. Older individuals who migrated at an advanced age tend to have a lower probability of choosing permanent settlement and are more likely to return to their home country (Dustmann 1996). This trend can be attributed to the strong ties that older migrants typically maintain with their home country, which may impede their integration into the host society compared to younger migrants (Snel et al. 2006). An alternative explanation is that age influences the acquisition of human capital. Younger migrants are more adept at acquiring specific skills and knowledge in the host country, a process that becomes more challenging with age due to reduced learning capacity. If this acquired human capital is not easily transferable to the home country's labour market, the decision to return becomes more complex and costly (Dustmann 1996). However, it is important to note that age may also have the opposite effect. For instance, Black et al. (2004) found that older Tamil migrants were unwilling to return to Sri Lanka due to their reliance on healthcare services in the UK. This, of course, depends on the migrant's legal status and access to healthcare services in their country of residence. Irregular migrants, lacking access to healthcare services, are more likely to consider returning (van Wijck 2008). This highlights the challenge of distinguishing between policy and non-policy factors. Factors traditionally viewed as non-policy, such as age or health condition, often overlap with policy-related elements, such as access to healthcare services, which is a policy decision.

With regards to the use of AVR programmes in the Netherlands, Leerkes et al. (2017) found that their use increased with age until reaching a peak around the age of 60, where the use of AVR programmes declined. Similar findings were found in Norway (Brekke 2015).

In relation to gender, both Leerkes et al. (2017) and Brekke (2015) found that male rejected asylum seekers were more likely to enrol in assisted return programs than women. The qualitative study of Black et al. (2004) looked at the relationship between gender and return migration decisions among various ethnic groups. Through interviews and focus groups, Black et al. (2004) found that most respondents did not perceive gender-specific aspects influencing their decisions regarding return. However, there were exceptions, with some expressing concerns about gender-specific issues in their home countries, such as the treatment of women or religious and cultural burdens. The study of Black et al. suggests that while gender-related concerns exist for some individuals, they do not appear to be significant determinants of return migration decisions across ethnic groups.

Stigmatisation. The risk of stigmatisation makes it challenging for irregular migrants to collaborate with returns. Brekke's interviews with employees of asylum reception centres in Norway (2015) revealed that some migrant groups consider enrolling in voluntary return programs shameful. According to the study, admitting that financial incentives influenced their decision to return could lead to a "loss of social standing" in their communities (p. 70). This perception is significantly influenced by group pressure, especially when migrants from the same nationality are concentrated in large numbers in reception centres. Additionally, returning home with money from assisted programs is viewed negatively in their home communities, as it labels individuals as "quitters" (p. 71). There is stigma both for enrolling in AVR programs and for not being successful in their migration journey (Schuster and Majidi 2013, van Houte and Koning 2008).

Various non-policy factors affect the migrants' decision to return voluntarily or wait for their return to be enforced. Even when return is enforced, some migrants opt to collaborate while others choose not

to. As evidenced in the reviewed literature, their willingness to return or collaborate with their return hinges on several factors: the socio-economic and safety conditions in the host country and in the country of return, their level of integration in the host country, their social network and personal circumstances (such as health, family, and children) and some subtle norms, such as the imperative to adhere to personal beliefs (challenged notions of nationality and citizenship), and community norms (such as the avoidance of stigmatisation).

Policy drivers of enforced return

The EU and its member states employ a range of return policies that span across various aims and scopes. These policies are designed to address the complex challenges associated with managing the return of migrants to their home countries.

Within this spectrum, return policies vary in their objectives and the extent of their application (Cleton, 2024). Some policies *directly aim* to increase the number of returns, focusing on enhancing deportation processes and enforcement mechanisms. Others *indirectly aim* to influence return rates by implementing measures to deter irregular migration or restrict access to certain social benefits for undocumented migrants.

Moreover, return policies may differ in their scopes, which determine the geographic and operational boundaries of their implementation. *Internal policies* primarily target activities within the borders of a specific country, focusing on strengthening immigration enforcement and border control measures. On the other hand, *external policies* extend beyond national borders and often involve collaboration with third countries. These external policies may include negotiating readmission agreements to facilitate the return of nationals from third countries.

This diversity in aims and scopes underscores the multifaceted nature of return policies and reflects the varied strategies employed by governments to effectively manage migration and returns within their respective jurisdictions. In what follows, we will assess the existing literature on the impact of these diverse policy approaches on enforced returns. It is important to clarify that our analysis will focus solely on the direct or indirect effects of return migration policies. We will exclude other policy areas outside the realm of migration, such as tax policies and economic policies. *Table 2* below summarises the policy determinants of enforced returns.

Table 2 Policy determinants of Enforced Return

Policy determinants of Enforced return		
Micro	Meso	Macro
<i>Perceived hardship of restrictive policies in host countries</i>	<i>Sanctuary cities, NGO presence</i>	<i>Assisted return programs (return counselling, economic incentives, return and reintegration programmes, “dual-track policy”)</i>
<i>Perceived enforcement of return policies (presence of police in reception centres)</i>		<i>Restrictive policies in the host country (difficulties in accessing employment, exclusion from social welfare policies, restrictive asylum policies, detention, regularisation schemes)</i>
<i>Perceived effectiveness of return and readmission agreements</i>		<i>Return and readmission agreements (credible incentives, perceptions of fairness and</i>

		<i>resonance with local population and needs)</i>
<i>Challenged notions of citizenship (length of residence)</i>		<i>Policy factors in countries of origin (policies stimulating return)</i>
<i>Perceived legitimacy of return migration governance</i>		

Assisted return programmes. At the internal level, EU member states have established a comprehensive return infrastructure to encourage voluntary returns. This infrastructure includes a significant number of social workers and/or NGOs dedicated to coaching potential returnees to make the decision to return (Kalir and Wissink 2016, Cleton and Chauvin 2020). Various strategies are employed for this purpose, including offering native return counselling by individuals of the same cultural background and speaking the same language as the potential returnees with the purpose of assisting them in making an informed decision but also in ensuring compliance with the return order (van Wijk 2008, Leerkes et al. 2017, Lietaert 2022). Additionally, intense and frequent conversations are conducted to encourage migrants to return promptly, under the premise that voluntary return is preferable to forced removal (Khosravi 2009). Coaches also aim to build personal relationships with returnees to understand their feelings and thoughts, allowing them to influence decision-making (Khosravi 2009). These tactics however can manipulate migrants' emotions and decisions rather than genuinely supporting them (Khosravi 2009).

Besides coaching, governments strive to encourage voluntary returns by giving economic incentives to migrants. This includes flight costs, a small amount for relocation expenses and in some cases, also post-return reintegration, such as support for business establishment, training, amongst others (Lietaert 2022).

The impact of incentives and assisted return programmes was found to be ambiguous in the study conducted by Koser and Kuschminder (2015). While respondents identified the benefits of voluntary return programs as one of the most influential policy factors in their decision-making process, the overall influence of policy measures on return decisions was limited. In fact, policy influences were ranked as the fourth out of five factors affecting the decision to return, preceded by conditions in the destination country, personal factors, and social factors.²

Like Koser and Kuschminder (2015), Brekke (2015) found that the decision to register for assisted return depended on several factors. These factors included conditions in the country of return and the country of residence, as well as the likelihood of enforced return. In comparison, the impact of return and readmission programs was minimal. For example, economic assistance had no effect on Afghans, who were unwilling to return due to the conflict in their country.

Brekke's (2015) study concluded that return and reintegration programs did not motivate rejected asylum seekers to return, but accelerated the return process for those who have already decided to return voluntarily. In such cases, economic assistance served as an additional incentive, prompting individuals to expedite their return to ensure they can benefit from the financial support.

Furthermore, research indicates that assisted voluntary return programs alone do not effectively promote returns unless they are complemented by a return decision. This coupling of assisted and

² However, in a non-published study, using regression discontinuity design Andersson, Jutvik and Martén (2021) find that cash grants can be associated with positive outcomes. The evidence in this topic is still unsettled. Manuscript on file with the authors.

forced return measures is known in the literature as the “dual-track policy” (Lietaert 2022). The underlying principle is that voluntary return is more likely to succeed when supported by the presence of forced return measures. Empirical studies, such as that by Black et al. (2011), attribute the success of the German return program to Bosnia and Herzegovina after the war’s end to the “rapid establishment of a credible forced return program” which encouraged migrants to opt for non-coercive forms of return (p. 10). Therefore, incentives to encourage return (the ‘carrot’) should be accompanied with disincentives (the ‘stick’). Consistent with this notion, Koser and Kuschminder (2015) demonstrated that migrants who deemed the possibility of deportation unacceptable were more inclined to opt for assisted return programs. The perception of being subject to something unacceptable only emerges because the state threatens with deportation.

Reasonable decision time. There are also policies that indirectly enhance the perceived legitimacy of migration governance among migrants. These policies focus on creating conditions that foster trust and transparency, thus encouraging voluntary compliance with return processes. For instance, a balanced duration of the asylum procedure could lead to the perception of decisions as just and reasonable. A reasonable decision time could help mitigate frustrations and suspicions among migrants, who may otherwise view the process as arbitrary or rushed (Leerkes 2016). These strategies are instrumental in promoting the perceived legitimacy of migration governance, ultimately leading to higher levels of cooperation and smoother implementation of return policies.

Restrictive policies in the host country. States also employ policies that affect the living conditions of irregular migrants in host countries which may have an indirect influence on returns. According to Koser and Kuschminder’s study (2015), returnees cited difficulties in accessing employment or other resources as significant factors influencing their decision to return home. However, this perspective may not apply universally to all irregular migrants, as it largely depends on the conditions awaiting them in their home countries or the conditions they were used to have. For example, a study conducted in a Dutch detention facility found that most detainees questioned the legitimacy of their deportation (Leerkes & Kox, 2017). However, a minority of detainees felt that their detention was beneficial for their life and health. They compared their conditions in the detention facility with their previous living conditions outside of detention and found the detention centre’s living conditions generally acceptable. Some even felt well cared for in these facilities (van Houte et al. 2021). Denmark, too, is known for its policies to try to manage irregular migrants by detaining them in remote “deportation centers” with minimal provisions (cf. Jørgensen, 2020).

Through interviews with native counsellors in the Netherlands, Van Wijk (2008) identified that policy factors, such as restrictive asylum policies, strict police surveillance of irregular migrants, and detention of aliens prompted irregular migrants to return. Similarly, regularisation schemes led many clients to delay or reconsider their return decisions when such schemes were being discussed in the Netherlands.

A more recent qualitative study, also conducted in the Netherlands, revealed that excluding rejected Afghan asylum seekers from social welfare policies did not incentivize their return (Kuschminder and Dubow 2023). This lack of motivation could be attributed to the challenging prospects of returning to a war-torn country. Therefore, further investigation is necessary to understand the impact of policy factors in the host country compared to the economic and safety conditions in the country of return.

It is important to recognize that the specific city within the host country where irregular migrants reside can significantly influence the enforcement of restrictive policies and the available alternatives. For example, certain cities in Europe are designated as sanctuary cities, actively opposing national government measures that curtail human rights, such as limiting access to housing and healthcare for irregular migrants (Oomen and Baumgärtel 2018, Ataç et al. 2020).

Furthermore, NGOs often operate in major cities, providing vital support and services to irregular migrants (van der Leun and Bouter 2015). While the presence of NGOs may mitigate the enforcement of restrictive measures, it may not necessarily reduce the occurrence of voluntary or assisted returns. In the Netherlands, for instance, receiving assistance from NGOs can actually increase the likelihood of voluntary returns. This is because NGOs typically condition their support on the cooperation of irregular migrants with the return process (van der Leun and Bouter 2015). Such requirements often stem from directives issued by local governments, which provide financial backing to these NGOs. Therefore, it is essential to consider the city-specific dynamics in further analysis.

Return and readmission agreements. At the external level, the EU and its member states often rely on the existence and implementation of return and readmission agreements with third countries. These agreements can influence decisions made by states regarding cooperation on returns. The effective implementation of these agreements can affect whether migrants decide to cooperate with their returns. If perceived ineffectively, migrants will likely not collaborate with returns. For instance, Brekke's study (2015) illustrates how some Eritreans and Somalians trust that Norwegian authorities will not deport them due to challenges in deporting them to their countries of origin. Similarly, van Houte et al. (2021) mention the case of a migrant detainee from Morocco who was not afraid of deportation because he believed it was unlikely to happen, relying on Dutch authorities to release him soon (also see Kalir, 2017).

From a theoretical perspective, the effectiveness of return and readmission agreements hinges on two pivotal factors: the existence of credible incentives for compliance (rational choice theory) and the perception of fairness and legitimacy among the parties involved (social learning model) (Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier 2004).

Existing research, though, indicates that many of these agreements lack meaningful incentives. Most agreements signed between member states (without the intervention of the EU) and third countries lack effective incentives (European Migration Network 2022), and even those agreements negotiated at the EU level often fail to offer substantial benefits (Lavenex and Wichmann 2009). For example, incentives like the prospect of EU accession or integration are primarily applicable to Eastern European and Western Balkan countries. However, Stutz and Trauner (2022) found, through simple statistical analysis, an increase in the return rate in these regions regardless of return and readmission agreements. Despite the presence of incentives such as visa facilitation or mobility partnerships, research has shown limited success in increasing the rate of enforced returns (Leerkes et al. 2022). This limited success could be attributed to factors such as the weakness of those incentives, as they hardly create legal paths for regular migration. Mobility partnerships, which were expected to fulfil this role, focus more on capacity building than on actual mobility, leading some scholars to refer to them as "immobility partnerships" (Poli and Cinelli 2017).

Qualitative research on southern perspectives suggests that return and readmission agreements are perceived as benefiting EU states primarily, raising questions about why third countries should collaborate with the EU on supporting their failed border control system (Reslow 2013).

Return and readmission agreements have a limited impact on return rates, highlighting the challenges in motivating migrants to return to their own countries. Despite efforts to encourage compliance through incentives, the effectiveness of these measures depends on the level of resonance or dissonance from the local population (Reslow 2013). Less resonance with return and readmission agreements complicates compliance, as adherence may encounter local resistance. Factors such as reliance on remittances and the level of democracy could influence government sensitivity to local opinion (Ellermann 2008, Roig and Huddleston 2007, Morrow 2007, Dai 2007).

The extent to which a third state influenced the negotiation of the agreement could also affect resonance. Active participation from third states ensures that agreements reflect their needs and concerns, thereby enhancing resonance with local needs. Agreements negotiated at the EU level are often presented to third countries as packaged deals with limited opportunity for the latter to influence their contents or direction (Billet 2010, Cassarino 2011, Reslow 2013). This makes it challenging for third states to ensure that these agreements resonate with their interests and concerns.

Furthermore, qualitative research indicates that certain incentives are viewed as fairer or more legitimate than others, depending on how well they align with the norms and values in the countries of origin and transit. For example, visa facilitation agreements may resonate well with certain populations, as shown by the research of Bolkvadze (2016) in Georgia, while linking development aid to cooperation with returns may face resistance, as evidenced by the study of Cham and Adam (2023) in Gambia.

Transitioning from informal to formal agreements can signal resonance, as informal agreements are used to “test the waters” and gauge the relationship between states (Zanker 2023).

Perceived enforcement of return policies. Besides the actual effectiveness of return and readmission agreements, the perceived level of actual enforcement seems to influence the number of assisted returns. Brekke’s study (2015) revealed that the visible enforcement of return decisions, such as the presence of police in reception centres, could lead to increased enrolment in voluntary return programs in Norway. However, the impact varied depending on nationality. While it encouraged enrolment among Chechens, it prompted Afghans to abscond and leave the reception centre, as revealed by interviews with employees in reception centres in Norway. Conversely, observing the deportation of individuals from different nationalities did not affect enrolment, particularly if returnees believed that their own nationality made deportation difficult (e.g., Eritreans or Somalis in Norway). This underscores the complex interplay between enforcement strategies and migrant responses, requiring nuanced approaches to address diverse needs and challenges.

Challenged notions of citizenship. Migrants’ resistance to established notions of nationality, citizenship, and state authority may hinder their return. The research of van Houte et al. (2021) shows that immigrant detainees awaiting deportation use denationalised and transnational definitions of citizenship and belonging to contest migrant admission requirements. Using these narratives, they engage in forms of resistance to deportation, ranging from direct actions like destroying identity documents or self-harm to more indirect methods such as hunger strikes. While direct resistance directly hinders return procedures, indirect tactics increase the cost and complexity of deportation for Dutch authorities. These tactics aim to garner public attention and support, especially when migrants are perceived as deserving or well-integrated, thereby making deportation challenging to execute (Rosenberger and Winkler 2014). Although van Houte et al.’s study does not explicitly explain why some migrants resist while others do not, there are indications within their research that the length of residence may be correlated with denationalised and transnational notions of citizenship and belonging.

Policy factors in the country of origin. The policies implemented in the country of origin can significantly influence migrants’ decisions to return voluntarily. For instance, policies addressing job opportunities, financial incentives, or housing assistance may serve as catalysts for migrants to return to their home countries (Jonkers 2008, Debnath 2016). However, it is crucial to note that these policies typically target highly skilled migrants and may not necessarily include irregular migrants or those in low-skilled occupations. Moreover, the effectiveness of such policies hinges on various factors, including the overall conditions in both the country of origin and the host country (Debnath 2016). For

instance, if the root causes that initially led the migrant to leave remain unaddressed, these return-oriented policies may fail to yield the desired outcomes (Debnath 2016, Kapur 2001, Pellegrino 2001). Conversely, if challenges in the host country align with incentives for returning, individuals may be more inclined to opt for voluntary returns, the development of the hi-tech industry in India had an important role together with further incentives in attracting expats working in that area abroad (Jonkers 2008). Thus, the interplay between policy measures, individual circumstances, and broader socio-economic conditions underscores the complexity of the return dynamics.

The literature reviewed indicates that policies have an indirect, rather than direct, impact on return. For example, migrants are more likely to participate in return programs if a return decision has been issued. In this way, return policies can indirectly encourage returns by creating a context of potential deportation, making assisted return programs more appealing. Policy factors do not operate in a vacuum but interact with various non-policy factors, such as economic conditions, social networks, and individual circumstances. Additionally, the perceived enforcement of return policies is crucial from the migrant's perspective. The mere existence of return and readmission frameworks does not necessarily lead to cooperation from third states regarding returns. Instead, the effectiveness of these frameworks depends largely on how strictly and consistently they are perceived to be enforced.

Section 2: Post-return Outcomes

Conceptualisation of post-return outcomes

Post return outcomes refer to what happens after return. Such outcomes can range widely from successful return to a failed return process. In light of this variation, it is important to set up some conceptual guideposts.

Some theorize sustainable return as the paradigm of a successful return process (Black and Gent 2006, OECD 2024). In sustainable return, the migrant returns to his home country and does not re-emigrate because his situation in the home country is safe and satisfactory, as the migrant “re-embeds” or reintegrates into his home society. Sustainable return then ties together the interests of states in controlling migration flows, the interest of the migrant in achieving good living conditions and the interest of the government and society of the home state, in seeing return migration as beneficial and fair, to the point of being willing to cooperate in such procedures (Black and Gent 2006, Chu et al. 2008, Ghosh 2001). The concept of “sustainability” used here parallels its used in development (i.e. sustainable development) where there is a move away from narrow metrics of success to formulas that incorporate the satisfaction of the interests of a wide variety of stakeholders.

By implication, failed return outcomes are those in which some parts (or all parts) of this formula break down. On one end of the spectrum, we can see that a return process that leads to the re-incidence of illegal migration does not prove to be successful, and signals policy failure on the part of the departing state. At the other end of the spectrum, an “effective” deportation process where the returnee is deported to conditions of poverty, insecurity, or persecution, and which is achieved only by force, fails to secure the future cooperation of governments and of society and attaches severe political costs on the departing state.

However, while the paradigm of sustainable return is of interest as a standard, it is difficult to operationalize or to realize in practice. Given that there are so many dimensions to the concept (psychological, social, economic) and so many actors and perspectives involved in its realization (those of the migrant, the origin country, the host state, and the international community), it is hard to come to judgment about better or worse return outcomes in concrete policy scenarios. In reality, virtually

every policy must stand somewhere in a continuum between being sustainable and thus successful, and unsustainable and thus a failure. But the concept is so complex that determining where precisely a policy falls is difficult or impossible.

To go around this problem, it may be beneficial to use more straightforward normative guideposts that may have a more immediate resonance. These may be found in the opposition between re-integrative and stigmatizing returns. Re-integrative returns are those that manage to successfully put the migrant back into the fabric of his home society. Stigmatizing returns are by contrast those where the return process marks the returnee as undesirable, as a failure or as a traitor, and ensure that he remains alienated in his home society. The concepts of reintegration and stigmatization are in some way used in the migration literature (on reintegration in the context of return migration see Kushminder 2017, on stigmatization see Schuster and Majidi 2013).

Having these guideposts in view, we now proceed to discuss the relevant literature on the determinants of post-return outcomes at the macro, meso, and micro levels.

Non-policy drivers of post-return outcomes

Cassarino (2004) introduces the concept of return preparedness, which is crucial for determining the success of migrants' reintegration and readmission in their home country. Return preparedness is influenced by various interconnected factors, with the contexts of both the host country and the country of return playing significant roles. Key aspects of preparedness include the migrant's *willingness* and *readiness* to return. By willingness, Cassarino (2004) refers to the desire to return, and by readiness, the comprehensive preparation and timing required for return.

Several factors influence the migrant's *preparedness* to return, including individual characteristics and structural factors in both the host country and the country of return. Individual characteristics include the accumulated economic assets, skills, experiences and social networks, and the duration and nature of the migration experience. Pre-return conditions, such as the migrant's legal status and ability to work in the host country, impact the migrant's ability to accumulate resources and thus can influence their preparedness to return and success in reintegrating.

Additionally, the policy and non-policy contexts in the country of return, such as political stability and economic conditions, play a critical role in determining its capacity to support the migrant's reintegration. The context in the host country, including the availability of return counselling, diaspora networks, and support for entrepreneurial activities, is also crucial (Haase and Honnerath 2016).

Thus, return preparedness involves more than just the desire to return (willingness); it requires comprehensive preparation and the right timing, taking into account the contexts of both the host and return countries (readiness). The framework of preparedness highlights the interplay of various factors at different levels.

The context in the country of return. A key factor influencing post-return outcomes is the level of safety found in the home society (Carr 2014, Riiskjaer and Nielsson 2008). If violence is widespread, there will be a strong incentive towards starting another cycle of migration and the human rights outcomes of returnees will be poor. Likewise, the availability of job opportunities in the home country is essential for successful economic reintegration (Nawaz and Tonny 2019). The existence of such

opportunities might depend on the availability of appropriate educational and vocational training programs in some part of the migration journey (Latek 2017).

Additionally, the economic situation in the country of return plays an important role in reintegration. During the repatriation of Namibians to their homeland in the 1990s, Arowolo (2000) noted that their repatriation put pressure on the already weak economy of a recently independent country. Most returnees were resettled in rural areas, which were isolated and distant from major cities where job opportunities were available. This created significant challenges for their integration, as they lacked the resources and skills necessary to start farming and earn a livelihood. *Table 3* below summarises the non-policy determinants of post-return outcomes.

Table 3 Non-policy determinants of post-return outcomes

Non-Policy determinants of Post-return outcomes		
Micro	Meso	Macro
<i>Individual characteristics: children, education, belonging to ethnic group, economic dependency on family members</i>	<i>Community and networks (reception by local communities, acquisition of new values and norms, maintenance of social networks in country of origin, occasional visits, negative stereotypes)</i>	<i>The context in the country of return: safety, economy, job opportunities, corruption</i>
<i>Migration journey: reasons for migrating and experiences in the host country (level of independence while in host country, time spent abroad, time since return)</i>	<i>Regular contact with relatives abroad</i>	<i>Experience in the host country (acquisition of new skills, corruption)</i>
	<i>Stigmatization (victims of human trafficking, domestic workers, the "survival guilt", negative stereotypes)</i>	
	<i>Competitors for scarce resources</i>	

Through interviews and focus groups with Iraqi Kurdish returnees from Norway and the United Kingdom, Paasche (2016) found that corruption in the country of return significantly affected the reintegration outcomes of returnees to Iraqi Kurdistan. Specifically, corruption hindered their ability to find employment and start entrepreneurial activities, as they were often asked for bribes or required to have connections to succeed in the selection process. This corruption impacted not only the economic reintegration of returnees but also their psychological reintegration. Some interviewees felt the need to re-emigrate to rebuild their identities, which had been adversely affected by their experiences of injustice and the lack of rule of law in the country. To avoid being targeted, Riiskjaer and Nielsson (2008) documented cases of Iraqi returnees who instructed their children not to reveal that they had lived in Denmark.

Experience in the host country and migration journey. Individuals' experience in the host country, and the acquisition of new skills, values and norms will affect their reintegration. For example, returnees who have become accustomed to living in a society with low levels of corruption may encounter psychological challenges when reintegrating into their home country with high levels of corruption. According to Paasche (2016), Iraqi Kurdish returnees often considered re-emigration as a

means to rebuild their identity, feeling out of place in the corrupt environment they encountered upon returning to Iraq Kurdistan.

The acquisition of new skills is associated with better reintegration outcomes (van Meeteren et al. 2014), while lack of them is usually reported as an impediment for reintegration (Schuster and Majidi 2013).

Besides the acquisition of skills, norms and values, live experiences during the migration journey also affect post-return outcomes. Based on accounts of refugees and migrants, Ghanmen (2003) points out that the reintegration process is influenced by both the past experiences of the returnee while fleeing and their experiences in the host country. For example, Iraqi Arabs who fled as political opponents may dream of returning to the country they left behind and because they see their refuge as temporary they have not worked in their integration in the host country. In contrast, Iraqi Assyrians who fled due to marginalisation and discrimination in their country do not dream of returning and they have succeeded in reintegrating into the host country. Returning for them will be more challenging than for Iraqi Arabs. Furthermore, experiences during the migration journey can complicate the reintegration process, particularly if returning triggers sad memories and reopens old wounds (van Houte and Koning 2008).

Furthermore, the level of independence that migrants had in the host country, particularly in choosing where to live and move around, significantly influenced their reintegration upon return (van Houte and Koning 2008). Those who had resided in asylum centres with limited mobility or work opportunities experienced greater difficulties integrating compared to those who had an irregular status and were hosted by families or friends in the host country. This latter group achieved higher levels of reintegration outcomes compared to those hosted in asylum centres.

Fleischer's (2013) research also shows that the longer time passed since return reduces the desire to re-emigrate, which could be explained by the fact that time helps in reintegration. That is why those that returned recently were more likely to consider re-emigration. Interestingly, the time spent abroad had no influence on the decision to re-emigrate.

Community and networks. The reception of returnees by their local communities is crucial. As highlighted by Arowolo (2000), the support provided by local chiefs significantly influences the reintegration experiences of returnees. In fact, lack of support from the community can seriously hinder their reintegration process.

As noted by Ruben et al. (2009), female return migrants encounter more obstacles in social and psychological integration compared to migrant families with stable family structures, which highlights the importance of familial support in the integration process and identity formation.

Returning migrants experience psychological shock (Carr 2014) and social dislocation (Nawaz and Tonny 2019) when returning to their original societies. Providing adequate information to potential returnees can help them prepare for their return, avoiding the shock of encountering a situation back home that differs greatly from their expectations (Muggeridge and Dona 2006). Additionally, the ability to maintain their social networks while abroad is a crucial factor in ensuring a successful return process (Carr 2014).

Given that migrants often idealise their returns, it is important for them to have access to accurate and reliable information about the situation in their countries of origin. For this purpose, contact with family and members is important, as they usually provide actual information on the situation of

the country. Occasional visits can help them develop a realistic understanding of the current situation, which will help with their reintegration (Ghanmen, 2003).

Furthermore, keeping contact with relatives abroad at least once a week increased the desire for re-emigration, as evidenced in the study of Fleischer (2013).

Individual characteristics. The study conducted by Ruben et al. (2009) and van Houte and Koning (2008) analysed a small sample of around 178 involuntary returnees to Afghanistan, Sierra Leone, Togo, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Vietnam using regression analysis. Van Houte and Koning (2008) defined involuntary returns as those that “did not manage to obtain a permanent permit to stay and, or return outside of their own personal desire”. This includes those that are “forcibly pushed out of the country, and those who were pressured to return by authorities or did not see a possibility to stay in the host country” (p. 11). The findings reveal that various individual characteristics significantly influence the reintegration levels of return migrants. Specifically, factors such as having children, higher educational attainment, and weaker identification with either a majority or minority ethnic group are associated with greater economic integration. Additionally, vocational and higher education positively contribute to psychosocial integration, highlighting the importance of education in shaping personal identity. However, despite its positive effects on economic and psychological integration, education paradoxically impedes social integration, as evidenced by reduced social contacts, suggesting a complex interplay of factors. This merits further investigation. In particular, considering the reasons for outmigration alongside individual characteristics may help explain why certain individual characteristics affect post-return outcomes. Understanding these relationships could lead to more effective reintegration strategies.

An IOM report (2015) highlights the challenge of aligning the skills acquired abroad with the demands of the labour market in the country of return. Therefore, possessing education may not always guarantee a positive impact on reintegration; its effectiveness depends on whether those skills and education align with the labour needs of the country of return (Arowolo 2000). From interviews and focus groups with Bangladeshi returnees, Nawaz and Tonny (2019) found that female returnees who had worked as domestic workers in Saudi Arabia faced difficulties finding jobs in Bangladesh. This was primarily due to the lack of certificates attesting to the skills and experiences they had acquired abroad.

Van Houte and Koning (2008) discovered that having education and work experience in the country of return prior to migration could assist returnees in reintegrating into the labour market. However, it is important to interpret this finding cautiously. They observed that in countries where this effect was notable, such as Afghanistan, Sierra Leone, and Vietnam, access to education was primarily available to the privileged few. Belonging to a well-connected family could have rather facilitated their economic reintegration. This observation aligns with the difficulties returnees face when reintegrating into highly corrupt societies (Paasche 2016).

Inability to secure wage employment is an important impediment to the full reintegration of returnees. The research of Fleischer (2013) on return migration to Armenia shows that the most important factor for Armenian returnees to consider re-emigrating was their financial situation upon return. Not having a job or being financially dependent on relatives either in the country of return or abroad, increased the desire to re-emigrate.

The number of children in a family can impact reintegration. For example, Arowolo (2000) discusses the case of returnee families from Namibia after their independence in the 1990s. These families were often so large that they could not be accommodated by relatives. This created pressure to

either split the family up and distribute members among various relatives or compel them to start independently with the few resources they had.

Stigmatisation.³ Ackermann (2003)'s research revealed that personal experiences of domestic and collective violence before and during armed conflict, along with their individual coping abilities and cultural strategies plays a significant role in shaping reintegration outcomes.

Stigmatisation of women who were (or were presumed to have been) prostituted or sexually violated impedes reintegration upon return (Macklin 2009). Public services are not necessarily adapted to the needs of those suffering from stigmatization. According to Decker et al. (2009), women who have been prostituted have difficulties accessing employment, mental care and general health care services. Nawaz and Tonny (2019) found that female returnees from Saudi Arabia to Bangladesh experienced difficulties being accepted by their families upon return. The way they earned money in Saudi Arabia, working as domestic workers, was viewed with low esteem, which affected their families' honour and often led to their exclusion upon return.

Returnees can be stigmatised just for having left the country in a situation of need. Ghanmen (2003) highlights the stigma that returnees often face upon their return. They are frequently associated with negative stereotypes, leading to fear among the population and potential employers that they may incite opposition and subversion within the community. Individuals who left during wartime may feel the need to conceal their departure due to feelings of guilt for leaving loved ones behind during the conflict. This sense of guilt is also felt by families, friends, and others who may perceive returnees as having enjoyed a privileged life abroad while they endured the hardships of war, creating strains in their reintegration process (Ghanmen 2003).

Stigma can also arise from returning with new ideas, which are seen as a departure from traditional norms and values. Van Houte and Koning (2008) described the case of an Afghan returnee who had studied in Russia. Upon his return, people stigmatised him for having graduated in Russia, fearing he might bring communist ideas. Returnees that come back to highly religious countries could immediately be put on spot if they do not show abidance to religious and cultural traditions, in terms of food, dressing and engagements with religious activities (van Houte and Koning 2008).

In countries of return, people often associate forced returns or those who return with few resources with criminality. They assume that if someone was sent back and failed to accumulate resources during their migration, it must be because they are criminals (Van Houte and Koning 2008). However, stigma is absent when returnees have had successful migration experiences. Instead of facing stigma, they gain social status for the skills they acquired abroad (van Houte and Koning 2008). The link between stigma and levels of readiness and willingness to return highlights the importance of return preparedness for successful psychological reintegration.

In Mali, deportees from Europe prefer to (initially) stay in the capital city 'as it provides geographical distance, anonymity, and potential autonomy' rather than going back to their home village (Schultz, 2021. 2022).

Besides stigmatisation, returnees may be viewed as competitors for scarce resources or as burdens that increase competition in the labour market, further complicating their reintegration (Ghanmen 2003).

³ Stigmatization can be related to both policy and non-policy factors. In the following section, we will address stigmatization linked to non-policy factors. Stigmatization related to policy factors will be discussed in the last section of this working paper.

Policy drivers of post-return outcomes

Host state policies can have an important impact on the post-return outcomes. As seen above, the capacity of migrants to plan their return and the way their return is perceived in their communities at origin countries have implications for their reintegration. Returnees that have been forced to return will likely experience more difficulties finding a job, may suffer from poverty and will most likely face social stigma. If the interest of host states is to ensure the sustainable return of migrants, forced returns should be kept to the minimum.

Here one can make an analogy with the principle of *ultima ratio* in criminal law. Since the costs of criminalization are extremely high and they make reintegration into society extremely difficult, criminalization should only operate in cases where no other option is available, as it has the tendency to produce negative outcomes for all stakeholders. The same should hold for enforced returns. In highly enforced returns, there is minimal emphasis on reintegrating the individual into their home country. Due to the difficulties in reintegration, this type of return could lead the individual to seek re-immigration, even through illegal means, to overcome an unsustainable situation at home.

Continuing the analogy with criminal law, the emphasis on enforcement without reintegration efforts could be seen as a retributive and naive preventive response to the perceived infraction of immigration laws. Retributive insofar the rules are applied as a simple “payback” to the unauthorized migration. Naively preventive insofar there is the expectation that being “tough on migrants” will reduce the incidence of migration. To the contrary there are reasons to think that a rehabilitative approach, that focuses on reintegrating the migrant into society is most likely to achieve sustainable outcomes, including the long-term prevention of irregular migration. *Table 4* below summarises the policy determinants of post-return outcomes.

Table 4 Policy determinants of post-return outcomes

Policy determinants of post-return outcomes		
Micro	Meso	Macro
<i>Individual's situation of irregularity in the host country (ability to save money)</i>	<i>Individual and family stigma associated with forced return and failed migration</i>	<i>Conditions of return: voluntary vs forced return (lack of preparedness, stigma, psychological problems linked to forced returns)</i>
<i>Understanding of the temporariness of the protection given by host state</i>		<i>Reintegration support in country of origin</i>
		<i>Reintegration support in host country. Return counselling. Come-and-see visits</i>
		<i>Legal protection in countries of origin</i>

The conditions of return: voluntary vs involuntary returns. The circumstances surrounding the migration process, including conditions upon return, significantly impact integration (Ruben et al. 2009). The study of Monti and Serrano (2022) shows that forced returnees to Senegal struggled with economic integration in their home country. This struggle can be attributed to the heavily enforced return process, which leaves insufficient time to prepare and mobilize resources, leads to loss of social

connections, and brings associated stigma. Regarding preparation time, it is noteworthy that the EU Return Directive offers a grace period after a return decision has been issued for individuals to prepare for their return. However, this period is not granted to apprehended irregular migrants, who face deportation instead. This underscores the difficulty of preparedness associated with forced returns.

Challenges in reintegration could increase the inclination for re-migration as observed by Schuster and Majidi (2013). Forced returnees often face difficulties in repaying debts from their initial migration. The pressure to repay debts, summed to challenges with economic reintegration, make re-emigration the only viable option for many forced returnees. Additionally, the lack of preparation for return can cause family disruptions, such as leaving children and family members behind in the host country. The need to support and reunite with them can drive forced returnees to re-emigrate. The stigma associated with a failed migration journey can be a high price to pay, not only for the returnee but also for their family, further incentivizing re-emigration. Van Houte and Koning (2008) found that forced returnees often suffer from stigmatization upon return, frequently being associated with criminal behaviour which hinders reintegration. In Sierra Leone, for instance, news quickly spread when someone returned handcuffed or under police supervision, exacerbating this stigma.

In contrast, voluntary returns may provide better prospects for reintegration, as individuals are likely prepared for the return and might have stronger social and family support networks. As highlighted by Meeteren et al. (2014) in their interviews with returnees to Morocco, those who returned voluntarily made conscious preparations to ensure their successful reintegration. They even carefully considered the feasibility of their plans before returning. Altrogge (2023) compared post-return outcomes of 12 returnees who made use of AVRR programs to 8 deportees, and found that both types of returnees experience overlapping reintegration challenges.

At the micro level, enforced return have negative or traumatic effects on returnees, in particular in relation to children. According to Zylstra et al (2022), involuntary returns can lead to psychological problems in children, which challenge reintegration. The results are based on a semi-structured interview with 17 children and their parents who were forced to return to Armenia. The research gave special attention to the perspective of children. Including the psychological problems we can note mourning for the loss of their former life, loss of a sense of belonging, feelings of unsafety, and increased emotional distance from parents.

Reintegration support in the country of origin and in the host country. Policies in the country of origin that aid reintegration can reduce the costs associated with the initial transition. For example, India and China offer housing facilities, access to credit, and job reassurances (Jonkers 2008). Ecuador for a time provided the option to bring personal belongings, furniture, and cars tax-free, which lowers the costs of moving from one country to another (Boccagni 2011). However, in a small study on returns to Nigeria, Bison (2022) reports that poorly implemented return programmes may actually worsen the vulnerabilities of migrants instead of promoting their integration, while migrants may also “reinforce” certain vulnerabilities in order to benefit from perceived advantages offered by the state or international organisations.

In addition to support in the country of origin, the host country can also play a significant role by providing assistance with training and entrepreneurial activities, which is the role of AVR(R) programmes. This support helps returnees start new businesses and prepare for job opportunities in their home country. However, research by Ruben et al. (2009) and van Houte and Koning (2008) reveals that this assistance has little effect on long-term reintegration. One reason could be that these programs fail to consider reintegration as a long-term process. Financial assistance only covers short-term needs and does not support the returnee through the entire reintegration process. Flight tickets only facilitate return and not reintegration. Business establishment support assumes that all migrants

are entrepreneurs, which is often not the case. Moreover, support typically ends after the final instalment, usually after one year, leaving returnees without continued assistance for long-term reintegration.

It is also important that returnees have accurate information about the job market situation in the country of return and how to access it (van Houte and Koning 2008). Return counselling can play a crucial role in the success of reintegration. Returnees usually get information about the country situation through family members and networks in the country of return.

Haase and Honerath (2016) emphasise the need for host countries and countries of origin to work together in assisting migrants in preparing for their return and reintegration, through for instance, come-and-see visits, which could prepare the migrant by familiarising them with the current conditions in their home country and helping them establish necessary connections and resources for a smoother reintegration.

Legal protection and corruption. At the legal level, migrants are likely to experience discrimination and various forms of abuse, including being targeted for corruption, theft, and other crimes (Setrana and Tonah 2014). As such, the ability of the legal system to protect migrants is a key factor for successful return. Because these forms of abuse arise from migrants being recognized as such and seen wealthy (Carr 2014, ECRE 2005, Muggeridge and Dona 2006, Riiskjaer and Nielsson 2008); consequently, privacy in the return process might play an important role (Carr 2014). Koning and van Houte (2008) found that returnees to Sierra Leone felt more comfortable returning to big cities, where their status as returnees could go unnoticed and they could access policy protection.

Individual's situation of irregularity. One key issue in determining post-return outcomes is the ability of the migrant to work and save money during the migration journey (Nawaz and Tonny 2019, Latek 2017, Carr 2014). This often depends on the migrant's legal status, as some migrants have to work and live irregularly, their ability to save money may be limited, which has then a negative impact on their ability to successfully reintegrate upon return.

When migrants have a clear understanding of the temporary nature of their migration journey, they are more likely to reintegrate upon return. Van Houte and Koning (2008) provide an example of returnees to Bosnia and Herzegovina who, when they received refugee protection in Germany, understood that it was temporary and that they would have to return when the war ended. This clarity regarding the expectations of their stay in the host country facilitated their reintegration afterwards.

Preliminary conclusions and further research

The review of the literature on return migration highlights several key areas where further research can deepen our understanding of the factors influencing enforced return and post-return outcomes.

First, a comprehensive assessment of the determinants of enforced return and post-return outcomes is needed. Current studies tend to focus on specific aspects, use small samples, or employ techniques that hinder generalization. The literature indicates that decisions to return depend on a variety of factors that cannot be isolated without affecting the results. Just as policies do not operate in a vacuum, individual decisions to return are context-dependent. Therefore, a thorough assessment should consider the contexts in both host and origin countries, policy developments in these countries,

the personal circumstances of migrants, including family and social networks, and their beliefs and perceptions that could affect their decision to return. Analysing the interplay of these factors requires a multi-level approach. Furthermore, since these factors may evolve over time, longitudinal studies are ideally suited to capture these dynamic changes. It is important to note that combining qualitative and quantitative research methodologies is essential to capturing the nuances of both enforced return and post-return outcomes effectively.

Second, most of the literature explores forced or assisted return programs as different administrative modes of return. However, these can be considered together as enforced return. Future research should explore whether the determinants and effects of both types of return are sufficiently different to keep them separate and/or identify aspects where they overlap.

Third, qualitative studies have reached contradictory conclusions regarding the effect of stringent policies in host countries on compelling individuals to return. This hypothesis has not been tested quantitatively, adding additional controls such as the number of NGOs and the status of the city (e.g., sanctuary city or not). Although NGOs and cities may mitigate these restrictions, they may not necessarily influence voluntary and assisted returns, especially if they condition welfare services on cooperation with return initiatives. This hypothesis warrants empirical testing.

Fourth, current research indicates that the impact of return and readmission agreements is limited, but comprehensive data is lacking. Future research should collect data on the scope of the agreement (citizens and/or third country nationals), the negotiation process (stakeholders involved) and implementation and monitoring mechanisms which are currently missing elements from existing inventories (Cassarino 2022; European Migration Network 2022). Assessing these aspects could help us better understand the effects of these interstate agreements. Additionally, further research should examine the effects of different types of return and readmission agreements—such as bilateral, EU-wide, binding, non-binding, with or without incentives, and with or without implementation mechanisms—on enforced return. It is particularly important to consider how these agreements are perceived in countries of origin and how such perceptions may impede or facilitate the negotiation and compliance with these agreements.

Fifth, future research could focus more on South-South return and readmission processes and outcomes, for example from Gulf countries to Ethiopia, and Iran or Turkey to Afghanistan (cf. De Regt & Tafesse 2015).

Sixth, qualitative research has shown the difficulties returnees face upon their return and proposed the need for coordinated action between countries of origin and return. A good way to facilitate such cooperation is through existing monitoring mechanisms of forced and voluntary returns and post-return outcomes. Monitoring the human rights situation of returnees is crucial for identifying and addressing violations or abuses they might face upon return, including protection against discrimination, violence, exploitation, and other forms of abuse. Additionally, post-return monitoring could aid in the sustainable reintegration of migrants into their home communities. Monitoring could also promote transparency in the return process and build trust among migrants, host countries, and countries of return, encouraging participation in voluntary return programs. Further research could explore the effect of human rights monitoring on influencing return decisions and post-return outcomes.

References

- Abaunza, C. M. (2024). Return migration and return intention in times of crisis: Dominican return during the COVID-19 pandemic. In *Return migration and crises in non-Western countries*, Yeo Jungwon (ed.) Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 193-213.
- Ackermann, L. (2003) 'Violence, Exile and Recovery: Reintegration of Guatemalan Refugees in the 1990s – A Biographical Approach', D. Phil. Thesis, unpublished. University of Oxford.
- Altrogge, J. (2023). Income prospect trajectories after state-induced return from Germany to the Gambia: Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration as 'slow deportation'. *sozialpolitik. ch*, (2/2023), 2-4.
- Arowolo, O. O. (2000). Return Migration and the Problem of Reintegration. *International Migration*, 38(5), 59–82. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2435.00128>
- Ataç, I., Schütze, T., & Reitter, V. (2020). Local responses in restrictive national policy contexts: welfare provisions for non-removed rejected asylum seekers in Amsterdam, Stockholm and Vienna. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 43(16), 115-134.
- Bastia, T. (2011). Should I stay or should I go? Return migration in times of crises. *Journal of international development*, 23(4), 583-595.
- Battistella, G. (2018). Return migration: a conceptual and policy framework. *International Migration Policy Report Perspectives on the Content and Implementation of the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration*, 3-14.).
- Billet, Carole (2010). 'EC readmission agreements: A prime instrument of the external dimension of the EU's fight against irregular immigration. An assessment after ten years of practice', *European Journal of Migration and law*, 12:1, 45-79.
- Bisong, A. (2022). Return, Precarity and Vulnerability in West Africa: Evidence from Nigeria. In: Teye, J.K. (eds) *Migration in West Africa*. IMISCOE Research Series. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-97322-3_11
- Black, R., & Gent, S. (2006). Sustainable return in post-conflict contexts. *International Migration*, 44(3), 15-38.
- Black, R., Collyer, M., & Somerville, W. (2011). Pay-to-go schemes and other noncoercive return programs: is scale possible. *Migration Policy Institute Paper*.
- Black, R., Koser, K., Munk, K., Atfield, G., D'Onofrio, L., & Tiemoko, R. (2004). Understanding voluntary return. *Home Office Online Report*, 50(04).
- Boccagni, P. (2011). The framing of return from above and below in Ecuadorian migration: a project, a myth, or a political device?. *Global Networks*, 11(4), 461-480.

Bolkvadze, Ketevan (2016). 'Cherry picking EU conditionality: Selective compliance in Georgia's hybrid regime', *Europe-Asia Studies*, 68(3), 409-440.

Brekke, J. P. (2016). Why go back? Assisted return from Norway. *Rapport 2015: 08*.

Carr, H. (2014). Returning 'home': experiences of reintegration for asylum seekers and refugees. *The British Journal of Social Work*, i140-i156.

Cassarino, J.P. (2004). Theorising return migration: The conceptual approach to return migrants revisited. *International Journal on Multicultural Societies (IJMS)*, 6(2), 253-279.

Cassarino, Jean-Pierre (2011). 'Resilient Bilateralism in the Cooperation on Readmission', in Marise Cremona, Jörg Monar and Sara Poli (eds.), *The External Dimension of the European Union's Area of Freedom, Security and Justice*. Brussels: Peter Lang, 191-208

Cassarino, J.P. (2022). Inventory of the Bilateral Agreements Linked to Readmission [Dataset]. Harvard Dataverse. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/VKBCBR>

Cassarino, Jean-Pierre (2011). 'Resilient Bilateralism in the Cooperation on Readmission', in Marise Cremona, Jörg Monar and Sara Poli (eds.), *The External Dimension of the European Union's Area of Freedom, Security and Justice*. Brussels: Peter Lang, 191-208.

Chu, B., Stec, K., Dünwald, S., & Loran, T. (2008). *Recommendations for the return and reintegration of rejected asylum seekers: lessons learned from returns to Kosovo*. Danish Refugee Council. Vester Kopi. Copenhagen.

Cleton, L. (2024). Conceptualizing EU Return Policy since 2000: time for a paradigm shift?. Finding Agreement in Return (FAiR), Deliverable 5.1.

Cleton, L. (2022). The time politics of migrant deportability: An intersectional analysis of deportation policy for non-citizen children in Belgium and the Netherlands. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 48(13), 3022-3040.

Cleton, L., & Chauvin, S. (2020). Performing freedom in the Dutch deportation regime: Bureaucratic persuasion and the enforcement of 'voluntary return'. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 46(1), 297-313.

Constant, A., & Massey, D. S. (2002). Return migration by German guestworkers: Neoclassical versus new economic theories. *International migration*, 40(4), 5-38.

Dai, X. (2007) *International Institutions and National Policies*. Cambridge, UK and New York: Cambridge Univ. Press. ix, 187 pp.

De Genova, N.P. (2002). Migrant "illegality" and deportability in everyday life. *Annual review of anthropology*, 31(1), 419-447.

De Haas, H., & Fokkema, T. (2011). The effects of integration and transnational ties on international return migration intentions. *Demographic research*, 25, 755-782.

Debnath, P. (2016). Leveraging return migration for development: The role of countries of origin—A literature review. *KNOMAD (Washington DC) Working Paper*, 17.

Decker, M. R., Oram, S., Gupta, J., & Silverman, J. G. (2009). Forced Prostitution and Trafficking for Sexual Exploitation Among Women and Girls in Situations of Migration and Conflict: Review and Recommendations for Reproductive Health Care Personnel. In *Women, Migration, and Conflict Breaking a Deadly Cycle*, Susan Forbes Martin and John Tirman (eds.), Springer Dordrecht Heidelberg London New York, pp. 63-86.

De Regt, M., & Tafesse, M. (2018). 'Deported before experiencing the good sides of migration': Ethiopians returning from Saudi Arabia. In F. Demissie (Ed) *Ethiopians in an age of migration* (pp. 104-118). Routledge.

Dustmann, C. (1996). Return migration: the European experience. *Economic policy*, 11(22), 213-250.

European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE) (2005) 'Increasing refugee participation in the field of voluntary return', available online at www.ecre.org.uk

European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE) (2018). *Voluntary Departure and Return: Between a Rock and a Hard Place*. Policy Note 13, August 2018.

Ellermann, Antje (2008). 'The Limits of Unilateral Migration Control: Deportation and Interstate Cooperation', *Government and Opposition*, 43:2,168-189.

European Migration Network (2022). Inventory on Bilateral Readmission Agreements signed by or entered into force in EU Member States in 2014-2021 [Dataset]. Retrieved from https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-10/EMN_inventory_for_bilateral_readmission.pdf

Fleischer, A., *The Role of the Family for Return Migration Reintegration and Re-emigration in Armenia* (Göttingen: Max Planck Institute for the Study of Religious and Ethnic Diversity, 2013).

Ghanem, T. (2003). *When Forced Migrants Return "Home": The Psychosocial Difficulties Returnees Encounter in the Reintegration Process*. 16.

Ghosh, B. (2001). *Return migration: journey of hope of despair*. Geneva: International Organization for Migration.

Haase, M., & Honerath, P. (2016). *Return migration and reintegration policies: A primer*. German Marshall Fund of the United States..

Hedstrom, P. (2005). *Dissecting the social: On the principles of analytical sociology*. Cambridge University Press.

Hemberg, J. (2022). *Return to what?: A quantitative analysis of how structural factors in countries of origin impact the probability of complying with a return decision among rejected asylum seekers in Sweden* (Master thesis). <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:su:diva-205608>

International Organization for Migration (IOM) (2015). *Reintegration-Effective approaches*. Retrieved from <https://www.iom.int/reintegration-effective-approaches>

Jonkers, K. 2008. "A Comparative Study of Return Migration Policies Targeting the Highly Skilled in Four Major Sending Countries." MIREM Analytical Report, European University Institute, Florence.

Jørgensen, M. B. (2020). "Representations of the refugee crisis in Denmark: Deterrence policies and refugee strategies". In D. Abdelhady, N. Gren, and J. Martin (Eds) *Refugees and the violence of welfare bureaucracies in Northern Europe*. Manchester University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7765/9781526146847.00011>

Kalir, B. (2017). State desertion and "out-of-procedure" asylum seekers in the Netherlands. *Focaal*, 2017(77), 63-75. <https://doi.org/10.3167/fcl.2017.770106>

Kalir, B., & Wissink, L. (2016). The deportation continuum: Convergences between state agents and NGO workers in the Dutch deportation field. *Citizenship Studies*, 20(1), 34-49.

Kapur, D. (2001). Diasporas and technology transfer. *Journal of Human development*, 2(2), 265-286.

Khosravi, S. (2009). Sweden: Detention and deportation of asylum seekers. *Race & class*, 50(4), 38-56.

Klinthäll, M. (2007). Refugee return migration: return migration from Sweden to Chile, Iran and Poland 1973–1996. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 20(4), 579-598.

Kos, S., Maussen, M., & Doornik, J. (2016). Policies of exclusion and practices of inclusion: How municipal governments negotiate asylum policies in the Netherlands. *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 4(3), 354-374.

Koser, K., & Kuschminder, K. (2015). Comparative research on the assisted voluntary return and reintegration of migrants. *International organization for migration*, 13.

Kuschminder, K., & Dubow, T. (2023). Moral exclusion, dehumanisation, and continued resistance to return: Experiences of refused Afghan asylum seekers in the Netherlands. *Geopolitics*, 28(3), 1057-1078.

Latek, M. (2017). Reintegration of returning migrants. *European Parliamentary Research Service*. Retrieved from [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2017/608779/EPRS_BRI\(2017\)608779_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2017/608779/EPRS_BRI(2017)608779_EN.pdf)

Lavenex, Sandra and Nicole Wichmann (2009). 'The External Governance of EU Internal Security', *Journal of European Integration*, 31:1, 83-102.

Leerkes, A. (2016). Managing Migration Through Legitimacy. In: *Irregular Migration, Trafficking and smuggling of human beings: Policy Dilemmas in the EU*, edited by Sergio Carrera and Elspeth Guild. Brussels: Centre for European Policy Studies.

Leerkes, A., Galloway, M., & Kromhout, M. (2011). Terug of niet? Determinanten van terugkeerintenties en-attitudes onder (bijna) uitgedoemde asielmigranten. *Mens en maatschappij*, 86(2), 122-156.

Leerkes, A., Van Os, R., & Boersema, E. (2017). What drives 'soft deportation'? Understanding the rise in Assisted Voluntary Return among rejected asylum seekers in the Netherlands. *Population, Space and Place*, 23(8), e2059.

Leerkes, A., & Kox, M. (2017). Pressured into a preference to leave? A study on the “specific” deterrent effects and perceived legitimacy of immigration detention. *Law & Society Review*, 51(4), 895-929.

Leerkes, Arjen, Mieke Maliepaard, and Manon van der Meer (2022), ‘Intergovernmental relations and return. Part 2: From paper to practice? EU-wide and bilateral return frameworks between EU+ and non-EU+ countries and their effects on enforced return’, Memorandum 2022-2, available at <https://repository.wodc.nl/handle/20.500.12832/3210>

Lietaert, I. (2022). Critical reflections on assisted return programmes and practices, in *Handbook of return migration*, King, R., & Kuschminder, K. (eds.), Edward Elgar Publishing, 108-121.

Macklin, A. (2009). Legal Aspects of Conflict-Induced Migration by Women. In *Women, Migration, and Conflict Breaking a Deadly Cycle*. Springer Dordrecht Heidelberg London New York.

Monti, A., & Serrano, I. (2022). Economic reintegration postreturn—examining the role of return voluntariness, resource mobilization and time to prepare. *Population, Space and Place*, 28(7), e2577.

Morrow JD. 2007. When do states follow the laws of war? *Am. Polit. Sci. Rev.* 101:559–72.

Muggeridge, H., & Doná, G. (2006). Back Home? Refugees' experiences of their first visit back to their country of origin. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 19(4), 415-432.

Nawaz, F., & Tonny, T. A. (2019). Reintegration challenges of migrants in Bangladesh: A study on forced returnee women migrants from Saudi Arabia. *Horizon*, 1(1), 49-58.

Newland, K. and B. Salant (2018), *Balancing Acts: Policy Frameworks for Migrant Return and Reintegration*. Washington, D.C.: Migration Policy Institute.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2020) Sustainable Reintegration of Returning Migrants: A Better Homecoming, Paris: OECD, <https://www.oecd.org/migration/sustainable-reintegration-of-returning-migrants-5fee55b3-en.htm>

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2024), Return, Reintegration and Re-migration. Understanding Return Dynamics and the Role of Family and Community, accessible at: <https://www.oecd.org/migration/return-reintegration-and-re-migration-625fb5e6-en.htm>

Oeppen, C. (2009) *A Stranger at Home: Integration, Transnationalism and the Afghan Elite*, Brighton: University of Sussex, unpublished PhD thesis.

Oomen, B., and M. Baumgärtel. 2018. “Frontier Cities: The Rise of Local Authorities as an Opportunity for International Human Rights Law.” *European Journal of International Law* 29 (1): 607–630.

Paasche, E. (2016). The role of corruption in reintegration: experiences of Iraqi Kurds upon return from Europe. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42(7), 1076-1093.

Paasche, E. (2018). Corruption and migrant returns. Managing risks in return programmes, Oslo: U4 Anti-Corruption Resource Centre, Chr. Michelsen Institute, U4 Brief, 1.

Paasche, E. (2022), Corruption and return migration, in: *Handbook of return migration*, King, R., & Kuschminder, K. (eds.), Edward Elgar Publishing, 185-198.

- Panke, D. (2018). Research design & method selection: Making good choices in the social sciences. *Research Design & Method Selection*, 1-368.
- Pellegrino, A. (2001). Trends in Latin American skilled migration: “brain drain” or “brain exchange”? *International migration*, 39(5), 111-132.
- Pluymen, M. (2002) Undocumented Migrants in The Netherlands (1.3.6.). in *Book of Solidarity* edited by PICUM.
- Poli, Sara, and Claudia Cinelli (2017). ‘Mobility and legal migration in the context of the European Neighbourhood Policy: What role for the European Union?’, *Revista de Derecho Comunitario Europeo*, 21:58, 979-1005.
- Reslow, Natasja (2013). ‘Partnering for mobility? Three-level games in EU external migration policy’, Doctoral Thesis, Maastricht University, <https://doi.org/10.26481/dis.20130905nr>
- Riiskjaer, M. and Nielsson, T. (2008) Circular Repatriation: The Unsuccessful Return and Reintegration of Iraqis with Refugee Status in Denmark, UNHCR, New Issues in Refugee Research, Research Paper No. 165.
- Roig, Annabelle, and Thomas Huddleston (2007). ‘EC readmission agreements: a re-evaluation of the political impasse’, *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 9:3, 363-387.
- Rosenberger, S., & Winkler, J. (2014). Com/passionate protests: fighting the deportation of asylum seekers. *Mobilization*, 19(2), 165–184.
- Ruben, R., Van Houte, M., & Davids, T. (2009). What Determines the Embeddedness of Forced-Return Migrants? Rethinking the Role of Pre-and Post-Return Assistance 1. *International Migration Review*, 43(4), 908-937.
- Schimmelfennig, Frank, and Ulrich Sedelmeier (2004). ‘Governance by conditionality: EU rule transfer to the candidate countries of Central and Eastern Europe’, *Journal of European Public Policy*, 11:4, 661-679.
- Schultz, S. U. (2021). “The adventure is not easy.” The Discretionary Politics of Social Suffering and Agency in Post-Deportation Narratives in Southern Mali. *International Journal for Crime, Justice and Social Democracy*, 10(3), 101-114. <https://doi.org/10.5204/ijcjsd.2044>
- Schultz, S. (2022). »Failed« Migratory Adventures?: Malian Men Facing Conditions Post Deportation in Southern Mali. Bielefeld: transcript Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783839460092>
- Schuster, L., & Majidi, N. (2013). What happens post-deportation? The experience of deported Afghans. *Migration studies*, 1(2), 221-240.
- Setrana, M. B., & Tonah, S. (2014). Return migrants and the challenge of reintegration: The case of returnees to Kumasi, Ghana. *Ìrìnkèrindò*, 7(Jun), 116-142.
- Snel, E., Engbersen, G., & Leerkes, A. (2006). Transnational involvement and social integration. *Global networks*, 6(3), 285-308.

Stutz, Philipp, and Florian Trauner (2022). 'The EU's 'return rate' with third countries: why EU readmission agreements do not make much difference', *International Migration*, 60, 154-172 <https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12901>

Tsuda, T. (2009) 'Introduction: diasporic return and migration studies' in T. Tsuda (ed.), *Diasporic Homecomings. Ethnic Return Migration in Comparative Perspective*, Stanford: Stanford University Press, pp. 1–18.

Van der Leun, J., & Bouter, H. (2015). Gimme shelter: Inclusion and exclusion of irregular immigrants in Dutch civil society. *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 13(2), 135-155.

Van Houte, M. (2014) *Moving Back or Moving Forward? Return Migration after Conflict*, Maastricht: Maastricht Graduate School of Governance, unpublished PhD thesis.

Van Houte, M., & de Koning, M. (2008). Towards a better embeddedness? Monitoring assistance to involuntary returning migrants from Western countries. *Center for International Development Studies, Amsterdam: CIDIN/AMIDSt*.

Van Houte, M., Leerkes, A., Slipper, A., & Breuls, L. (2021). Globalised citizenship and the perceived legitimacy of immigration control: narratives and acts of resistance in immigration detention. *Migration Studies*, 9(3), 1269-1291.

Van Meeteren, M., Engbersen, G., Snel, E., & Faber, M. (2014). Understanding different post-return experiences: the role of preparedness, return motives and family expectations for returned migrants in Morocco. *Comparative migration studies*, 2, 335-360.

Van Wijk, J. (2008). *Reaching Out to the Unknown; Native Counseling and the Decision Making process of irregular migrants and rejected asylum seekers on voluntary return*.

Webber, F. (2011). How voluntary are voluntary returns?. *Race & Class*, 52(4), 98-107.

Yendaw, E. (2013). A study of the underlying determinants of return migration of international return migrants to the Berekum Municipality, Ghana, *International Journal Sociology and Anthropology* 5(7): 249-261.

Zakirova, K., & Buzurukov, B. (2021). The road back home is never long: Refugee return migration. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 34(4), 4456-4478.

Zanker, F. (2023). A typology of resistance: the 'hot potato' of European return in West Africa. *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 1-20.

Zijlstra, A. E., Bonhage-Talsma, G. T., Post, W. J., & Kalverboer, M. E. (2022). Forced Return of Embedded Asylum-Seeking Families with Children to Armenia from a Children's Rights Perspective: A Qualitative Study of Their Developmental Needs and Best Interests. *The International Journal of Children's Rights*, 30(2), 577-603. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718182-30020003>

Zimmermann, S. E. (2017). Reconsidering the problem of 'Bogus' refugees with 'Socio-economic Motivations' for seeking asylum. In *Mobilities and Forced Migration* (pp. 35-52). Routledge.